

Experimental measurement of the loads on tidal turbines using conditions derived from field measurements

David M Ingram, Brian G Sellar, Chris Old, Tom Davey, Roman Gabl, Laura-Beth Jordan, Ophélie Nourrisson, and Stephane Paboef

Abstract—Tidal turbines are typically conservatively designed leading to additional, associated, expense. Over-design is commonly driven by a limited understanding of the conditions at the deployment site. The RealTide project aims to tackle this conservative design by producing an open-access database of field and experimental data, providing a fuller understanding of the spatial and temporal variation of these conditions and the interaction of real-world conditions with the turbine. Under this project, high resolution Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) have been deployed in the Fromveur passage (France) alongside the Sabella D10 tidal device. When interpreted using a high resolution three-dimensional TELEMAC model of the tidal environment, a number of both typical operational and energetic conditions have been identified. These results show that the influence of waves subjects even bottom mounted turbines to large variation in velocity. Tests in FloWave have been conducted under representative conditions that combine multi-directional waves with noncolinear currents. A highly controllable, three-bladed, model turbine has been tested under these conditions, with device power and force measurements. The RealTide database has been populated with information about the real world and experimental conditions and the response of and loads experienced by the turbine. This data provides a set of information that may be applied to the design of real-world devices deployed in the ocean. The device data is complemented by a set of, spatially dense, acoustic Doppler velocimeter measurements characterising the model turbine's inflow, near field, and wake. Particular attention is paid to ensuring the resulting open-access database is correctly quality assured and practical to access, providing maximum benefit for academic and industrial users alike.

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D. M. Ingram is at the Institute for Energy Systems, School of Engineering, The University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom (e-mail: david.ingram@ed.ac.uk).

B. G. Sellar is at the Institute for Energy Systems, School of Engineering, The University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom (e-mail: Brian.Sellar@ed.ac.uk).

C. Old is at the Institute for Energy Systems, School of Engineering, The University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom (e-mail: C.Old@ed.ac.uk).

T. Davey is at the FloWave Ocean Energy Research Facility, The University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh United Kingdom (e-mail: tom.davey@flowave.ed.ac.uk).

R. Gabl is at the FloWave Ocean Energy Research Facility, The University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh United Kingdom (e-mail: roman.gabl@ed.ac.uk).

L. Jordan is at the FloWave Ocean Energy Research Facility, The University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh United Kingdom (e-mail: L.Jordan@ed.ac.uk).

O. Nourrisson is at Sabella, Brittany, France (e-mail: o.nourrisson@sabella.bzh).

S. Paboef is Head of Composite Materials Section, Bureau Veritas - Marine & Offshore Division, Nantes, France (e-mail: stephane.paboef@bureauveritas.com).

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I. INTRODUCTION

CURRENT design and maintenance approaches for tidal turbines tend to be extremely conservative, resulting in expensive, over designed devices. The approach followed by technical specifications such as IEC TS 62600-2, and the BV NI603 (Current and tidal turbine) and DNVGL-ST-0164 (Tidal Turbines) rules is a direct result of the lack of experience at sea coupled with a poor understanding of the environment at deployment sites. Both these short comings increase the required safety factors. Reductions in safety factors and requires a more complete understanding of tidal conditions and the spatial and temporal variation of these conditions. If reductions in safety factors can be realised across a wide range of sub-systems significant cost reductions and performance benefits can be achieved. This requires some aspects such as the impact of turbulence on both fatigue loading and the accelerations experienced by the power take off system and rotor components to be better understood.

In recent years measurement campaigns have been undertaken at locations such as the Falls of Warness [1] and the Fromveur passage [2] alongside the deployment of large prototype and full scale devices. These measurements show turbines are subjected to a complex loading environment caused by the combined impact of tidal currents, large and small scale turbulence and ocean waves. As part of the RealTide project high resolution Acoustic Doppler Current Profilers (ADCPs) have been deployed in the Fromveur passage alongside the Sabella D10 turbine. Using the approach shown in Fig 1, and described in detail by Draycott et al [3], these measurements have been interpreted using a high-resolution, 3D, TELEMAC regional oceanographic model, allowing a number of typical operating and extreme conditions to be identified.

These conditions have been recreated in the FloWave basin combining multi-directional waves with non-collinear currents [4], [5] and tests are currently being conducted using a highly controllable, 1.2m diameter, three bladed model turbine developed by the University of Edinburgh [6]–[8]. The instrumented turbine records blade bending moments, shaft torque and thrust. The turbine is supported by a monopole mounted on a six degree of freedom (6-DoF) load

Fig. 1. Diagram depicting the process of utilising site data to drive the conditions simulated in engineering tools. [3]

cell. Force measurements are combined with wave gauge data and flow velocity information from acoustic Doppler velocimeters (ADV).

Load information combined with results from computational fluid dynamic simulations of the turbine (including an electrical model of the controller and the power train, see [9]) has been used to assess and classify the loads to which the full scale turbine is subjected [10]. It is hoped that these results will lead to significant cost reductions enabling hydro-kinetic tidal energy converters to be commercially deployed at scale.

All the experimental data summarised in this paper, together with the derived loads, a detailed characterisation of the upstream conditions in FloWave, and results from numerical simulations are publicly available as part of the RealTide database.

II. FIELD MEASUREMENTS

Real-world observations are the core data on which site characterisation, site development, and Tidal Energy Converter (TEC) design and development are based. Field measurement methodologies [11]–[14] build on the large knowledge base developed in oceanography and off-shore sectors [15]. Sites being developed for tidal stream energy extraction are inherently high-energy and highly variable in both space and time [1], [16]–[18]; standard oceanographic instruments are not optimally designed to operate in these conditions [19], [20]. Building on knowledge from the EPSRC FloWTurb (EP/N021487/1) and ETI ReDAPT projects, deployment methods have been developed to optimise data quality within the operating constraints of the instruments, and post-processing methods have been implemented to extract key environmental parameters from the field data [1].

Tidal flow measurements are typically collected using an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP). These instruments use acoustic transducers arranged to produce a set of divergent “beams” along which the velocity is estimated from the Doppler shift in the back-scattered signal of a transmitted acoustic pulse. The three Cartesian velocity components are reconstructed from the “beam” data using trigonometry, with the key assumption that the velocity field is spatially homogeneous across the horizontal area covered by the beams. This assumption is valid away from areas where flow instability generates coherent structures with scales comparable to the water depth, and is fundamental to the accurate operation of ADCPs. It is this assumption

Fig. 2. Deployment of an Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler (ADCP) package from a DP lifting vessel in the Fromveur Passage (left). Detailed view of the package showing the gimbal support, lifting eye, battery/data package and the two ton concrete support.

that is questionable at the majority of high energy tidal energy extraction sites for significant periods of time. [20] showed that a divergent beam ADCP acts as a spatial filter to eddies with length scales relevant to tidal stream energy devices, and calculated that the total energy can be underestimated by up to 35% at typical rotor heights. This has significant implications for both energy yield and turbine loading calculations.

Deployment and recovery operations for instrument packages (like those shown in Fig 2) at tidal sites are constrained and high-risk making them costly. Consequently, instruments are deployed at discrete measurement points making it infeasible to capture full flow conditions of the site from instrument deployments alone. An appropriately designed, calibrated, and validated numerical hydrodynamic model of the site complements the field measurements and provides information content required to correctly interpret the data. Conversely, the hydrodynamic model provides insight into optimal instrument placement and areas to avoid given the operating limitations of the instruments in complex flow conditions. Other external factors [15] also limit where instruments can be deployed. Most field measurements, therefore, represent some form of compromise between cost, risk, and data quality and coverage.

Fundamentally TECs convert tidal stream kinetic energy into electrical energy through an electro-mechanical system (e.g. rotor driven generator). The fluid state to which the TEC is exposed depends on more than just the tidal forcing. The coastal sites where TECs are being developed are typically exposed to open-ocean storm-generated swell, local wind generated waves, large-scale coherent flow structures that

result from boundary separation processes, and shear generated turbulence. These processes operate across a wide range of frequencies and length scales, operating at different times scales to the tidal forcing. Consequently these non-tidal processes modify the fundamental tidal flow altering the power performance of the TEC and imposing additional structural loads that impact on mechanical fatigue [7], [21]. Combining site measurements and hydrodynamic models allows the key physical processes to be separated and parameterised [1]. The parameters extracted can be used to inform control conditions for physical experiments in flumes and basins and to provide boundary conditions for advanced Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models.

Parameter extraction requires the deconstruction of the complex signals recorded by the oceanographic instruments into process-dependent signals. The main instrument used for site measurement is the acoustic Doppler profiler (ADP); this measures a vertical profile of the 3-D velocity field at a single location. An ADP typically has a built-in pressure sensor which provides a proxy measurement for the surface elevation. The velocity signal can be broken down into the component physical processes and expressed as:

$$\vec{u}(\vec{x}, t) = \vec{u}_{tide}(\vec{x}, t) + \vec{u}_{dyn}(\vec{x}, t) + \vec{u}_{wave}(\vec{x}, t) + \vec{u}_{turb}(\vec{x}, t) \pm \sigma_{\vec{u}} \quad (1)$$

where $\vec{u}(\vec{x}, t)$ is the measured velocity data, \vec{u}_{tide} is the tidal flow produced by the tidal forcing of the Earth-Moon-Sun gravitational system, \vec{u}_{dyn} is the flow associated with the dynamical response of the fluid to boundary interactions and hydraulic readjustments, \vec{u}_{wave} are the orbital velocities associated with surface gravity waves, \vec{u}_{turb} are the velocity fluctuations due to the energy cascade response to internal shear, and $\sigma_{\vec{u}}$ is the measurement uncertainty due to instrument noise, numerical rounding, instrument bias, *etc.*

Whilst the wave component, \vec{u}_{wave} , is often considered only important for near surface devices, data from the Sabella turbine (Fig 3) shows the impact of passing Atlantic swell on a seabed mounted turbine can be significant. Data from the EMEC site collected by the ReDAPT project showed a similar influence of waves on the DeepGEN IV turbine. In this work we distinguish between \vec{u}_{dyn} and \vec{u}_{turb} , although they are both components of the unsteady turbulent flow. Essentially \vec{u}_{dyn} represents the large scales of turbulence associated with the large scale energy containing eddies shed by islands and formed by fluid jets emerging from channels and straights into more open water. These structures are very large having length scales more than twice the rotor diameter and frequencies of less than 0.1 Hz. Thomson *et al* [22] report that these large, anisotropic, essentially two dimensional, eddies are advected through the site without participating directly in the energy cascade. Table I gives representative magnitudes of the velocities for the various processes as a percentage of the tidally driven flow. These values are for the EMEC Tidal Energy Test site, and are derived

Fig. 3. Time histories of normalised wave height and turbine power output for the Sabella D10 turbine located in the Fromveur Passage, Brittany, France.

from *in situ* measurements and a 3-D regional model of the site for TEC operating flow speeds.

TABLE I
MAGNITUDE OF VELOCITY ASSOCIATED WITH DYNAMICAL PROCESSES RELATIVE TO TIDAL FLOW.

Process	Relative Magnitude (%)
Dynamic	5 to 20
Waves	7 to 15
Turbulence	6 to 9

Similarly the surface elevation signal can be broken down by process and expressed as:

$$\eta(\vec{x}, t) = \eta_{tide}(\vec{x}, t) + \eta_{atm}(\vec{x}, t) + \eta_{dyn}(\vec{x}, t) + \eta_{wave}(\vec{x}, t) \pm \sigma_{\eta} \quad (2)$$

where $\eta(\vec{x}, t)$ is the measured surface elevation, η_{tide} is the surface elevation due to the tidal forcing, η_{atm} is the surface response to variations in atmospheric pressure, η_{dyn} is the surface variations that result from the dynamic response of the fluid to flow accelerations, η_{wave} is the surface elevation due to gravity waves, and σ_{η} is the measurement uncertainty.

Some or all of these processes can be replicated in engineering design modelling (*e.g.* physical scale models, Blade element momentum theory (BEMT) models, or CFD models of rotor blades, turbines, structures, *etc.*). Typically the input conditions for design models are parameterised [9], [23], [24]. These parameters are extracted from the component signals of the deconstructed field observations. In this paper we will show how the field data are used to design tank test experiments that use a physical scale model of a TEC to determine the response to realistic environmental conditions.

The scaled TEC model used in the experiments [6] is based on the DeepGEN IV turbine deployed at the Falls of Warness, Orkney, as part of the ETI ReDAPT project. The extensive data set collected during this project forms the basis of the environmental conditions database developed in the RealTide project that has been used to parameterise site conditions. The conditions to be represented in the tank tests cover a range

Fig. 4. Overview FloWave including the definition of the global coordinate system and the directions in the tank.

of flow speeds encountered at a tidal site, a variety of sea states (*i.e.* wave height, period and direction, and spectral form), and, if possible, a representative level of turbulence. From the field measurements the range of hub-height flow-speeds (covering both spring and neap tidal flows), histograms of significant wave-height vs wave period, and the range of turbulence intensity are derived. These parameters characterise the site. Not all observed environmental conditions can be replicated in a test tank facility, so conditions included in the tests are selected to be representative and informative.

III. FLOWAVE TESTS

A. Facility

Testing was conducted at the FloWave Ocean Energy Research Facility at The University of Edinburgh, Scotland. The FloWave facility is a circular basin, 25 m in diameter and 2 m deep, designed to conduct combined wave-current testing with offshore renewable energy devices (Fig. 4). It is equipped with 168 active-absorption wave makers located around the 360-degree perimeter of the facility along with 28 flow drives (also in a circular arrangement) generating current across the central test area and recirculating under the tank floor (Fig. 5). The inner part of this floor, with a diameter of 12 m, is raisable and allows a dry installation of equipment and models. The wave and current systems can be independently controlled, allowing the recreation of realistic and directionally complex wave-current sea states.

All locations for the tank based datasets are referenced based on a consistent global coordinate system, which is introduced in Figure 4. The origin of the right handed coordinate system is in the centre of the tank when it is submerged and the z-axis is positive upwards. Consequently, the still water surface has a positive z-value of 2 m. The x-axis is pointing along the flow direction of 0° (from the workshop/offices to the back of the tank). Wave gauges, and arrays thereof, are normally attached along the gantry, which is parallel to the y-axis of the global tank coordinate system. A typical installation of the turbine is on the 6-degree of freedom (DoF) force platform (FP), which is installed with a centre of (1.65,-0.55,0)=(*x*, *y*, *z*). Wave and current can be produced in any directions.

Fig. 5. Schematic top view and cross section of FloWave [8].

FloWave provides a high flexibility of the independently controllable and combinable wave and current. Inherent turbulence levels are similar to those at sea which together with good repeatability makes it an ideal environment for the testing of single or multiple turbine (arrays) [7], [8], [21]. Further example projects are the investigation of floating structures [25], testing of remotely operated underwater vehicle (ROV) [26] as well as the development of novel measurement instrumentation to improve the velocity mapping in the tank [27]. This dataset contained within the RealTide database incorporates both tests with a tidal turbine (loads and local flow measurements) and “open tank” tests in the absence of the turbine, concentrating on characterising the ambient flow conditions.

B. Instrumentation and quality control

A big challenge for the creation of a general database is the wide range of measurement equipment, which can differ in type as well as number of deployed devices. Each individual technique also includes a specific quality control to ensure that the data is checked and provides a high accuracy. In this section, the main instrumentation types as well as the typical methods to ensure the quality are described. The four groups are: (a) free surface elevation, (b) velocity, (c) motions as well as (d) Turbine forces and moments.

1) *Free surface elevation*: The standard measurement instrument to capture the changes in the free surface elevation are conductive wave gauges (WG). Up to 16 locations can be captured simultaneously with a very high accuracy of smaller than 1 mm. Typically, those measurements are included in the tank software and are available immediately after the test run. If real-time monitoring of the wave field is required five gauges

Fig. 6. Measured tidal speeds (black line) and DeepGEN IV turbine power (blue line) - shown as five minute averages - acquired in October 2014 in ambient (non-turbine affected) conditions at the Fall of Warness, Orkney. Red dots highlight tidal conditions where mean current speed (averaged over 20 metre span centred at mid-depth) are approximately 3.1 m/s (scaling to 0.8 m/s at FloWave).

can be connected to the National Instruments data acquisition system through Churchill wave monitors. For most experimental investigations a measurement frequency of 128 Hz is used. For each deployed WG the following information is needed: $[x,y,z,elevation]$. The coordinates are in most of the cases a constant and connected to the gantry position but it is also possible to add similar instrumentation onto a floating model [28].

The high accuracy is ensured by a regular five point calibration of the WG in 50 mm steps. This is conducted at the beginning of every experimental day and provides a calibration record with the goodness of the linear fit.

2) *Velocity*: Velocity measurements were undertaken with two Nortek Vectrino Profiler acoustic Doppler velocimeters (ADV) operating in single point mode and measuring in three dimensions. The ADVs used a sampling rate of 96Hz, and data were collected in 20 minute batches for all wave-current sea states at a given measurement location. These batch files were later split to individual files for each sea state. An extra 30 seconds of data collection after each sea state run time was carried out to ensure the entire test duration was captured. For current only sea states, ADV data were collected in individual files for each measurement location, capturing 5 minutes of primary data collection, as well as the additional 30 seconds mentioned above. The ADVs were synchronised as per the manufacturer's guidance to prevent acoustic interference. The ADVs were spaced 600 mm laterally (y axis), equating to $0.5D$. The ADVs were equipped with downward sampling heads on 1 m flexible cables, supported on carbon fibre tubes. Both instruments were mounted to a frame which could be traversed laterally and vertically (y and z axes) on the gantry. The longitudinal (x axis) position was varied through movement of the gantry.

The measurements locations in the vertical and streamwise plane are indicated in Fig. 7 in relation to the tidal turbine model. Lateral measurements (cross flow) were taken every 300 mm across the rotor plane. The arrangement of two ADVs was designed to facilitate time-efficient collection and support this extensive data gathering exercise. In addition to being spatially dense in three dimensions, the dataset is especially powerful as it captures (a) the inflow conditions; (b)

the near-field conditions across the rotor plane; and (c) the turbine wake.

3) *Motion*: FloWave can provide two different motion capturing (MoCAP) systems, namely an above and underwater system provided by Qualisys. Both concepts are based on the 2D-capture of reflective markers illuminated by infra-red or blue (underwater) light. In this work, the underwater system was used on selected tests to monitor movement in the ADV mounting hardware, allowing excess vibration to be identified and quantify the frequencies of any oscillations. Six underwater floor mounted underwater cameras provide data at a typical sample rate of 128 Hz in the form of $[x,y,z,Rx,Ry,Rz, residual]$ for each body.

4) *Turbine power, forces and moments*: Load data was obtained from three sources: a 6-DoF force plate giving foundation loads; a torque-thrust transducer in the turbine nacelle; and root bending moment (RBM) transducers on each blade measuring flapwise loads.

Foundations loads in 6-DoF $[F_x,F_y,F_z,M_x,M_y,M_z]$ were measured using an AMTI OR6-7 1000 force plate, mounted flush with the floor and logged at 128Hz unless otherwise noted.

The instrumentation in the model turbine is fully described in [29]. In summary, the force/thrust transducer (a bespoke unit supplied by Applied Measurements Ltd.) is mounted upstream of all seals and bearings to eliminate frictional losses from the measurements. When combined with the measured angular velocity the instantaneous power may be correctly determined. This is illustrated in Figure 8 for an opposing irregular wave in combination with current. The RBMs were built from a custom flexure instrumented by Applied Measurements Ltd, again described in [29].

Force measurement devices are either periodically recalibrated, or a check with known weights/loads is conducted to verify they are operating correctly.

5) *Turbine control and monitoring*: The model tidal turbine (as illustrated in Fig. 9 undergoing deployment) was operated in angular velocity control model across Tip Speed Ratios (TSRs) "sweeps" from 3 to 7. The nominal velocity at hub height was used for determining the turbine angular velocity, as provided from calibration data obtained by [4]. Feedback of the angular velocity, recorded in revolutions per minute (RPM), is provided by a 14-Bit incremental quadrature

Fig. 7. ADV measurement locations in the streamwise and vertical dimension, expressed in terms of turbine diameter D and mm.

Fig. 8. Example time series of tidal turbine power output and co-located wave surface elevation at laboratory scale for an inflow of 0.8 m/s in an opposing irregular sea.

Fig. 9. The model tidal turbine undergoing deployment in the FloWave facility with raisable floor partially submerged (March 2021)

encoder processed on National Instruments cRIO chassis.

6) *Synchronisation*: Where possible all instrumentation is synchronised using a TTL rising edge digital pulse supplied by the tank upon commencing each experimental run. Data capture times are typically

set several seconds longer than the experimental time to aid post-processing, and therefore there may be some discrepancies in the duration on different channels. However, the tail end of the experiment may be trimmed to give consistent length while maintaining synchronisation.

Some instruments, notably the ADVs when paired together, are not capable of accepting the digital tank start trigger. In this particular case the ADVs were started manually and their output to the DAQ was recorded to provide an offset time.

C. Sea state selection and recreation

When translating real world conditions into a tank such as FloWave, the independent control of the wave and current must be considered. A baseline current velocity (i.e. magnitude and direction) is trivial to recreate - potentially with some iteration required for a given location in the tank if not previously calibrated. However, parameters such as turbulence intensity and velocity depth profile cannot be independently controlled in FloWave. Indeed, this capability is rare outside of a few specialised flumes (e.g. [30]). The flow conditioning system is a very substantial structure encompassing the entire circumference of the tank at a diameter of 25 m (illustrated in Fig. 5). Hardware driven modification of turbulence (e.g. through active vane control or interchangeable inlet grids) is generally impractical (or uneconomical) at such scale. A target scaled current speed of 0.8 m/s (3.1 m/s full scale) was implemented. This speed has been observed to commonly occur in an open and re-shareable data set available to the project, comprising a re-analysis of ADCP measurements providing ambient current conditions acquired during ReDAPT at the Fall of Warness, Orkney in October 2014. Figure 6 shows the depth-averaged tidal speeds for 28 days and shows that 3.1m/s flow speed captures the established peak flow regime for both the flood tide (during days 7 to 13) and the ebb tide (during days 23 to 28). Having selected 0.8 m/s as the target tank condition at FloWave a central wave period/s can subsequently be selected

that allow recreation of opposing and following wave-current conditions.

Much of the site-specific recreation lies in the translation of the wave condition into the tank. In FloWave, as with most wave tanks, the sea state in the frequency domain through an energy spectrum, optionally combined with a directional distribution if short-crestedness of sea states is a consideration. These spectra may be non-parametric (e.g. [31]) and built directly from site measurement (e.g. from wave measurement buoys), or as is more common from parametric spectra (e.g. JONSWAP) defined by summary statistics. It is this latter approach that was deployed here. These summary statistics (e.g. significant wave heights, peak periods) were selected based upon datasets available to the Realtide project for real world deployment sites.

Fig. 10. Occurrence (nearest %) of combined wave conditions, H_{m0} and T_p , from the Fall of Warness, Orkney at ambient flow speeds of 3.1 m/s (0.8 m/s tank scale) from winter 2014. Blue squares show wave conditions of completed tank tests [32]. The red circle shows the wave height and period of the regular wave used in the high-resolution mapping test (Fig. 7.). Light-blue patch is indicative of observed conditions for more exposed tidal energy sites.

The RealTide database also contains raw and post-processed data of tank wave-current conditions and resulting scale model performance from previous tests e.g., multiple irregular wave tests completed under EPSRC FloWTurb (EP/N021487/1), as reported in [32] and shown overlaid on measured H_{m0} and T_p wave conditions from the Fall of Warness, Orkney in Fig. 10.

The chosen spectra is recreated in the tank as a pseudo-random time series (i.e. a deterministic process with the phase of each frequency provided by a seed number driven random number algorithm) which ensures repeatability of the tests for the ADV mapping process. Additional variables which must be defined are the mean-direction, repeat time and run time. The repeat time reflects the fact that the translation from the frequency domain into the tank results in a periodic time series. The analysed window from the test should be an integer number of repeat times (typically a single repeat for each run). The repeat time is chosen as compromise between efficiency (shorter test) and a fuller description of the tail of the wave height

distribution for extreme wave heights and responses (longer tests). The run time is set to approximately 30 s longer than the analysed window to allow transient conditions during tank startup to be excluded.

The challenge when examining combined wave-current seas is that the wave spectrum is defined in the absence of current and will therefore be transformed by wave-current interaction when measured at the model location [5]. There are two approaches: establish the boundary condition from numerical modelling or measurement and assume the wave-current in the tank is representative of the real-world; or back-transform the site location wave conditions to account for wave-current interactions and give the correct boundary input. While the first approach is perhaps more elegant in principle, the data is not typically available (at least not as physical measurements). Therefore the latter approach is used here. The current induced modification of wave height for each frequency bin in the spectra was calculated as described in [33] to provide a corrected boundary input spectrum. Wave gauge arrays provide data for validation of these conditions, and quantification of any discrepancies.

IV. DATA MANAGEMENT AND ACCESSIBILITY

One of the main goals of the RealTide project is to improve access to key data sets that will aid and advance development of the tidal energy sector. There has been a large amount of data collected through legacy projects, numerical simulations run, and tank test experiments, but this information is rarely archived or made accessible to the key end-users - the developers. Given the strong dependence at all stages of development on data, there is a need for a set of good-quality, open-access data that can be used by the sector for a range of development and design tasks.

The conceptual design for the database is to collate metadata from the data archive into a set of relational tables, these metadata tables can be queried to identify the data fragments and corresponding archived files that contain the information that meets the users request. The result from the query is then passed to a separate process that extracts the information from the data archive, packages it in a standardised format, and returns it to the user. The data archive includes both the underlying unprocessed data and the corresponding physical characterisation parameters that are extracted by post-processing. There is a level of data fragmentation required to support this approach, this is an integral part of the data post-processing and standardisation.

Data management covers everything from the quality assurance methods used to collect the best data possible, through data capture, quality control of the collected data, to data standardisation and post-processing to extract key parameters. It is important to highlight the distinction between *data* and *information*. The data are the raw measurements made or the output from a numerical simulation; these are typically information-rich. The extraction of the information content typically requires expert knowledge to post-process the data, e.g. the extraction of wave parameters

from a pressure sensor data set. An appropriately designed database forms the link between the managed data and the associated information content, improving *accessibility* to the wider community. It is the information content that we aim to make more accessible to the developers, while retaining the underlying data for R&D activities.

Fig. 11. Data management process used to assemble the RealTide data set.

Building on a methodology developed in the ReDAPT project, all of the data (field measurements, tank tests, and modelling) have been collated, standardised, and archived (see Figure 11). Quality Assurance takes place prior to the instruments being deployed or the simulation run to ensure that the correct data is being measured and the physical and numerical sensors are properly calibrated. Once the data has been collected it is cleaned up (removing drop-outs and corrupted data) before a quality control (QC) check is done. Data which has passed QC process is converted into a standardised form from the proprietary formats in which it was collected. RealTide uses NetCDF (Network Common Data Form) version 4 [34] to store data. NetCDF is a self describing, portable, compact, scalable, extensible and achievable data format which is supported by programming interfaces for platforms including R, Matlab and Python.

Once the quality assured data has been archived on the data store in the NetCDF format, scripts are run which characterise the data, recording the resulting metadata into a SQL database together with pointers to the NetCDF file.

This process allows a user to query the SQL database, for example requesting all thrust measurements obtained for flood tide conditions with moderate waves. The SQL database returns a list of data-files covering the specified criteria and a script combines these into a NetCFD file. This file seeks to combine complimentary sets of data covering field measurements, physical scale model simulations, and numerical simulations. The authors believe that this approach to data management will significantly improve accessibility to data and has the potential to assist both researchers and developers working across the sector. The meta data links real-world measurements of a TEC response to environmental condition, with the corresponding physical model simulations and numerical simulations against a sub-set of the observed conditions.

Tidal processes vary on times scales from minutes to years, and on spatial scales from centimetres to 10s of kilometres. The design models used in this sector are generally not able to replicate tidal dynamics, *i.e.* they assume a constant mean flow and run for short

Fig. 12. Core entities used to construct the RealTide database of field, tank, and model data.

time scales (minutes). To allow specific site conditions to be characterised, the field data are fragmented on a time scale that allows the key physical processes to be resolved without imposing aliasing. For each time fragment the characterisation parameters are calculated and stored in post-processed data records. By default the tank test data and numerical simulation data are already time fragmented, so the post-processing extracts the corresponding physical parameters required to construct the conditions database. The information content is link through a pre-defined set of common metadata. The metadata allow the selection on all information related to a set of user-defined conditions from any or all of the data sources.

Fig 12 is a schematic of the core entities used to build the conditions database, full details are given in [35]. The common entity linking the field, tank and simulation data is the configuration record. Moving upward through the relational tree splits out the different methods for generating data. Moving downward through the relational tree are entities that are common to all data collection processes, with the root being the metadata that allows conditional searching of the data archive.

The result of a query is a list of time fragments and their corresponding parameter and data records. A separate process takes the query result and extracts the relevant data from the archive to produce an output that is returned to the user. Data fragments identified are collated into standardised netCDF output files [35]. From these standardised files the data can be converted to a report or alternate data formats, depending on the end-use requirements.

V. APPLICATIONS

The aim of the work conducted by the RealTide project has been to develop an open access database of archival quality field measurement, experimental and simulation data. The Online interface to the SQL database enables users to construct queries searching for specific operating conditions based on the meta data, while the associated tool chain assembles and delivers data to the end user.

This database provides a major step forward for tidal energy researchers as the architecture allows straight forward access to data for the first time. Previously entire data-set had to be downloaded from an archive

and post processed using proprietary tools - limiting the use of the datasets. The combination of quality assured, quality controlled data from the field, experiments and simulations can provide a more detailed understanding of the impacts of turbulence and waves on turbines.

Validia Camacho *et al* [10] used the data from FloWave experiments and CFD simulations to calculate a range of non-dimensional quantities and their associated time histories. Figures 13 and 14 give examples of this analysis.

Fig. 13. Derived power spectrum of the non-dimensional Centre of Effort ($CE_r = 2CE/D$) ratio for a range of tip speed ratios.

Fig. 14. Derived probability density functions of the tower drag coefficient $C_{D_{tower}} = 2(R_x - F_t)/(\rho Z_t D_t U^2)$.

The Centre of Effort, CE , is the point through which all of the forces acting on the tidal turbine, and its support structure, appear to act. This can be normalised with respect to the radius of the turbine to give the dimensionless centre of effort ratio, $CE_r = 2CE/D$. Fig 13 shows the frequency spectrum of CE_r plotted against the non-dimensionalised frequency. This non-dimensionalisation not only generalises the force spectrum but allows the frequencies associated with the blades passing the tower to be clearly identified. It should be noted that the low TSR case ($\gamma = 3$) had a different set up in comparison with the higher TSR runs. This anomaly has been rectified as part of a recent test campaign so the data included in the RealTide Database will be consistent. The 1P and 2P, 4P and 5P frequencies can easily be identified in the spectra. It should be noted that tower shadowing suppresses the 3P spike in this case.

While such frequency spectra are a useful tool for designers, knowledge of the probability distributions of loads is important for the design process. Fig 14 shows the kernel density estimate of the Probability Density Function (PDF) obtained from the non-dimensionalised tower drag time-histories. It is clear that the PDF is normally distributed and that the standard deviation is proportional to the TSR. The mean of the PDF converges towards $\overline{C_{D_{tower}}} = 0.5$ as the TSR increases. PDFs like this enable designers to make use of probabilistic design tools and to build 95% and 99% confidence intervals for the loads experienced by the turbine.

Such dimensionless, normalised, data that has been derived from computational models and experimental campaigns based on measured conditions at real deployment locations provide an invaluable tool for designers. It is hoped that the underlying data will provide the research community with a foundation to further explore the behaviour of the next generation of tidal turbine designs under realistic operating conditions.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

For the first time an open access, searchable and extensible, quality assured and controlled database of field measurements, experimental data and CFD simulation results has been produced. The databases web-based interface¹ allows the metadata to be searched for flow conditions of interest and for results to be returned to the user in a self describing NetCDF file.

Met-ocean data in the database is drawn from comprehensive instrument deployment campaigns, designed with the support of high resolution regional met-ocean models. The measurements include complex flow conditions where waves, large scale turbulence and strong shear profiles have significant impacts on deployed devices.

Post processing of the met-ocean data has enabled the design of representative, scale, test conditions which have been set up in the FloWave Ocean Energy Research facility and used as boundary conditions for both unsteady CFD simulations and blade element momentum theory calculations of the forces acting on the turbine. Quality assured and controlled results from both the experiments and CFD simulations have been included in the database.

Finally, we have given an example of post processing the experimental and CFD data from the database to obtain non-dimensional load spectra and load probability density functions that can be used to assist in the design of the next generation of tidal turbines, helping to eliminate over-design and improve maintenance planning leading to reductions in the levelised cost of energy.

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